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Guidance document for the local co-design and co-learning workshops (including local stakeholder analysis)

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Summary

The Sino-European CLEARING HOUSE project aims to provide evidence and tools that facilitate mobilising the full potential of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) for rehabilitating, reconnecting and restoring urban ecosystems. To achieve this goal, the project will establish a collaborative learning process on UF-NBS and develop a comprehensive co-design and co-learning system to connect policymakers, business, citizens and experts across China and Europe. This document - deliverable D3.1 ?Guidance document for the local co-design and co-learning workshops (including local stakeholder analysis)? - aims at presenting and describing how to involve local stakeholders and citizens in a UF-NBS research project and to promote solutions for sustainable urbanization. This guidance document shares the developed methodologies for co-design and co-learning workshops, and provides practical ways to identify and analyse target stakeholders both in China and Europe. The deliverable is structured in three main parts. The first part introduces the UF-NBS definition, CLEARING HOUSE project, workshops and explains the importance of stakeholder engagement. The second part presents the methodology and implementation of the co-design workshops, including its objectives, process, suggested agenda and intended target stakeholders. The third part describes the methodology of the two co-learning workshops. This document may be updated during the project lifetime appropriately, and the version number will be listed clearly in the version history timetable. This deliverable is linked to several annexes, including templates for preparing the co-design meetings, facilitating the activities and discussions, and reporting. These templates are available at the CLEARING HOUSE Co-design Community page at the Zenodo.org open access platform (https://www.zenodo.org/communities/ch_co-design/).

Approval

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Sino-European CLEARING HOUSE project aims to provide evidence and tools that facilitate mobilising the full potential of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) for rehabilitating, reconnecting and restoring urban ecosystems. To achieve this goal, the project will establish a collaborative learning process on UF-NBS and develop a comprehensive co-design and co-learning system to connect policymakers, business, citizens and experts across China and Europe. This document - deliverable D3.1 'Guidance document for the local co-design and co-learning workshops (including local stakeholder analysis)' - aims at presenting and describing how to involve local stakeholders and citizens in a UF-NBS research project and to promote solutions for sustainable urbanization.

This guidance document shares the developed methodologies for co-design and co-learning workshops, and provides practical ways to identify and analyse target stakeholders both in China and Europe. The deliverable is structured in three main parts. The first part introduces the UF-NBS definition, CLEARING HOUSE project, workshops and explains the importance of stakeholder engagement. The second part presents the methodology and implementation of the co-design workshops, including its objectives, process, suggested agenda and intended target stakeholders. The third part describes the methodology of the two co-learning workshops. This document may be updated during the project lifetime appropriately, and the version number will be listed clearly in the version history timetable.

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PURPOSE OF THE GUIDANCE DOCUMENT

This document presents how local stakeholders can be involved in a research project related to sustainable urbanization through applying urban trees and urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS). The co-design and co-learning workshops methodology has been developed within the Sino-EU CLEARING HOUSE project and is being implemented by 5 European and 5 Chinese cities or regions.

This document aims to share the developed methodology, so that any city or region interested in planning, designing or implementing UF-NBS in a collaborative way, can follow and adapt this approach, and join a global community of local living labs which will emerge from the CLEARING HOUSE project and similar projects.

This guidance document includes general guidelines and tips for successful events, targeting stakeholders, a sample agenda, and templates for the workshop sessions. These annexes are available at the [CLEARING HOUSE Co-design Community page](https://www.zenodo.org/communities/ch_co-design/) at the Zenodo.org open access platform (https://www.zenodo.org/communities/ch_co-design/).

KEYWORDS

co-design, co-learning, participation, transdisciplinarity, workshops, stakeholder, green infrastructure, urban forests, nature-based solutions, public participation, participatory research, participatory decision-making, Europe, China

ABBREVIATIONS

UF-NBS	Urban forests as nature-based solutions
NbS	Nature-based solutions

KEY DEFINITIONS

Urban forests: tree-based urban ecosystems that address societal challenges, simultaneously providing ecosystem services for human well-being and biodiversity benefits. Urban forests include peri-urban and urban forests, forested parks, small woods in urban areas, and trees in public and private spaces.

Nature-based Solutions (NbS): Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are defined as “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits”. (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016)

Urban tree: usually long living woody organism, usually single stemmed, with the potential to growing at a site in the urban or peri-urban area. This includes roadside trees, trees in squares, parking lots, or in parks and private gardens. Urban trees appear as individual trees, or as groups of trees.

Urban Forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS): a subset of nature-based solutions that build on tree-based urban ecosystems to address societal challenges, simultaneously providing ecosystem services for human well-being and biodiversity benefits. UF-NBS include peri-urban and urban forests, forested parks, small woods in urban areas, and trees in public and private spaces.

1 Introduction to the workshops

1.1 Urban Forests as Nature-based solutions

Nature-based Solutions (NbS) are defined as “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits”. (IUCN, 2018). This includes sustainable urban drainage systems, green walls, green roofs, but also urban tree-based solutions. Urban Forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) are a subset of nature-based solutions that build on tree-based urban ecosystems to address societal challenges, simultaneously providing ecosystem services for human well-being and biodiversity benefits. UF-NBS include peri-urban and urban forests, forested parks, small woods in urban areas, and trees in public and private spaces. UF-NBS comprise every measure a city can take to address urban development challenges by deploying tree-based ecosystems.

Trees and forests are a proven nature-based solution that contribute to sustainable urban development. Their potential for delivering ecosystem services, enhancing biodiversity and contributing to the wellbeing of urban societies is often underestimated and underused as for the most part in Europe and in the recent centuries, urban trees have usually mainly been considered for their aesthetic qualities. Now ideas have evolved and society seems more receptive to the idea of trees (and urban forests) as vehicles for urban improvements and quality of life. Urban trees and urban forests provide multiple benefits at a time: for example providing shade, filtering air pollution, increasing sales rates in retail, and reducing costs in public health care.

However, to do so, the planning, design and management of urban forests and urban trees need to be well-thought and adapted to the local conditions and the demands by the local society. This is where co-design and co-learning approaches are useful trajectories to increase the impact of urban forests as nature-based solutions.

1.2 The CLEARING HOUSE project

Building on the strengths of urban forests as nature-based solutions, the project addresses a global challenge that unites European and Chinese cities in their quest to develop more resilient cities and livable societies in order to improve human wellbeing. CLEARING HOUSE provides evidence and tools that facilitate mobilising the full potential of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) for rehabilitating, reconnecting and restoring urban ecosystems.

1.3 Why involve local stakeholders

Generally, the term ‘stakeholder’ refers to groups, organizations, institutes or persons that must be taken into account by governments or leaders (Bryson, 2004). Stakeholder participation is becoming increasingly embedded in national and international environmental policy, programmes and projects as it can help decision makers understand the needs, challenges and opinions of the people who are affected by the policies programmes and projects, and who will influence the outcomes of these (Reed *et al.*, 2009). Related to urban forestry, stakeholders are mainly involved in:

- Identifying the local needs and demands on urban forests and nature-based solutions;
- Identifying opportunities and expected impacts related to urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS);

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- Clarifying potential conflicts on UF-NBS design & planning, implementation (including investment) and management;
- Co-designing and/or co-managing new or existing urban greenspace;
- Monitoring the outcomes and impacts of urban forests as nature-based solutions.

The stakeholders that will be involved in our CLEARING HOUSE project are mainly policy makers, businesses, citizens and civil society organisations, experts and researchers. Indeed, beyond agreeing on the importance of setting up participatory processes for policy-making, the CLEARING HOUSE methodology stresses the need to promote the participation and collaboration of a variety of local actors, from all sectors of society. This approach, commonly referred to as the Quintuple Helix approach in the literature (Iaione, 2017), allows for the pooling of resources and knowledge of local actors in order to co-design urban services and infrastructures. Our approach: co-design and co-learning

The co-design and co-learning workshops will be organised both in China and Europe, and each workshop will bring together city administrations, policymakers, civil society groups and scientists, among others. The workshops will contribute to outline the most critical questions to be analysed during the project, and define the requirements for the tools and actions to be developed by the project.

What is the co-design method?

Co-design represents a useful methodology to foster close collaboration with stakeholders and explore the challenges related to the planning, design, establishment and management of UF-NBS. Co-design supports brainstorming on new ideas and collaboratively developing solutions that meet stakeholders' needs. Thanks to their collaborative processes, co-design workshops stimulate collective creative-thinking skills and represent a clear, simple and agile method that ultimately helps to create better solutions for the stakeholders and by the stakeholders. In CLEARING HOUSE, the co-design workshops are aimed at exploring the state of urban forests as nature-based solutions in the case study cities, and should focus on gathering input from participants to co-formulate relevant questions for the research done by CLEARING HOUSE.

What is the co-learning method?

Similarly, the co-learning method rely on the same collaboration instruments in order to allow for a participatory learning process that benefits both local stakeholders and policy-makers. In the framework of the CLEARING HOUSE project, the co-learning methodology will serve as an instrument to allow for an open and collaborative process of knowledge sharing between the partners in charge of research on UF-NBS and local stakeholders. The methodology indeed allows on the one hand for researchers and policy-makers to present the main challenges and results obtained from their analysis of UF-NBS; on the other hand it allows local stakeholders to complement and provide feedback on this research through structured group discussions.

With this guidance document, we want to share the approaches applied in our project. We are aware that the following co-design and co-learning methodology can be further improved. The method we develop below is indeed a snapshot of the work done to date rather than a finished and complete methodology.

The virtues of the approach

The importance of the co-design approach is more than ever recognized, especially in public policy programmes. The participation of key local stakeholders plays an essential role in the planning and implementation of solutions in urban areas both in Europe and in China. Such a participatory approach constitutes nowadays a common best practice recognized by European and Chinese urban planning and international policy frameworks such as the Urban Agenda for the EU and UN Habitat III New Urban Agenda.

The virtues of the co-design and co-learning approach can be summarized through the following points:

- Create people-centred designs: thanks to its participatory processes that involve the end-user or beneficiaries, this method allows to design solutions that closely respond to stakeholders needs and expectations;
- Ensure accountability and transparency of local authorities: policymakers and researchers are held accountable for their decisions thanks to a collaborative process that reduces the barriers between the policy and society realms;
- Foster cooperation among main actors: this method allows for the breakdown of administrative, political and social silos by bringing together different types of local stakeholders;
- Design solutions that are more sustainable and more efficient in the long-run: thanks to an inclusive and people-centred decision-making process the solutions designed will be less likely to suffer from conflicts and implementation failures.

The CLEARING HOUSE co-design and co-learning roadmap

The roadmap for local co-design and co-learning within the project is characterized by three main phases:

1. Local co-design workshop series (June-September 2020)
Objective: Gather all relevant actors and stakeholder groups to explore the context of UF-NBS in their cities, outline major challenges related to the progress and implementation of UF-NBS as well as challenges related to the governance of these solutions.
2. First series of local co-learning workshops (June-September 2021)
Objective: Introduce the research work on UF-NBS to be conducted through the project in the local case;
3. Second series of local co-learning workshops (February 2023)
Objective: Report and discuss findings from the analysis of UF-NBS with local stakeholders and citizens.

2 Co-design Workshop: Methodology

2.1 Objectives of the co-design workshop

The main objectives of the workshops are to understand the current challenges of urban forests in the city/region studied, to identify some of the existing urban forest tools, the benefits and costs, and the actions to be taken.

2.2 Process

2.2.1 Overview

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Process

Figure 1: The process of the workshops

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The workshops will engage city representatives with key stakeholders from research, policy, practice and civil society. They should work together to fill out four templates, detailed below.

2.2.2 Step 1: Major challenges to progress, implementation, governance & management

During this first session, participants discuss the main challenges to urban trees and urban forests in the local area. These challenges are clustered along nine themes (see Figure 2). Facilitators should review the terms in advance and familiarize themselves with the local situation. For example, participants may be confused about what the term “natural catastrophic events” includes. In this case, it is better to go with a broader definition, so that the local situation of as many case studies as possible is accommodated.

Major challenges to progress, implementation, governance & management	
	Natural catastrophic events:
	Wildfires:
	Insects & diseases:
	Invasive plants:
	Climate change:
	Social factors:
	Planning, maintenance & management:
	Urbanisation / Development / Competing interests:
	Finance:
	Other:

City:

CLEARINGHOUSE
中欧城市森林应对方案

Figure 2: Major challenges to progress, implementation, governance & management

2.2.3 Step 2: Assessment of current tools & impacts of urban forests

The second session is an assessment of the current situation related to urban forests and urban trees. This template is divided into two sections:

- which existing green infrastructure tools and policies exist;
- what wider impacts of urban forests (benefits and costs) do the stakeholders appreciate.

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Assessment of current tools & impacts of urban forests							
Existing green infrastructure tools & policies							
	Biodiversity	Climate change	Land use	Mapping	Mgmt & maintenance	Monetary assessment of costs	Other
What exists							
What works							
To be improved							

Wider impacts of urban forests (benefits & costs)	
Social:	
+	-
+	-
Ecological:	
+	-
+	-
Economic:	
+	-
+	-

City

Figure 3: Assessment of current tools & impacts of urban forests

For the top section of the template, the goal is to find out not only what the existing tools & policies are for the city/region, but which of these are working and which could be improved. This knowledge provides a background of where each case study is coming from, and what other case studies could be doing. As many tools and policies may not be strictly labelled as “urban forest” tools and policies, the term “green infrastructure” was used to widen the scope, and the tools are clustered along six themes: biodiversity; climate change; land use and planning; mapping; management & maintenance; monetary assessment of costs; and other. It is not expected that a city will have something for each of these. The reason broad themes were selected is that, for example, policies on biodiversity could have a potential impact on urban forests, as could policies to mitigate or adapt to climate change. However, these policies would most likely not strictly be just for urban forests, which is a much narrower field. By broadening the scope, the goal is to have a much more comprehensive understanding on the current situation.

The bottom section on “Wider impacts of urban forests (benefits & costs)” is meant to assess both the positive and negative impacts of urban forests. Benefits are the positive impacts related to urban forests, including ecosystem services provided by urban trees and urban forests. Costs – or negative impacts – include as well monetary costs (e.g. costs for pruning trees, or costs related to falling trees), as disservices¹ by urban forests and urban trees. The impacts are further divided into three categories: social, ecological, and economic. Examples are below:

- Biodiversity loss => ecological cost
- Improved health => social benefit
- Negative impact on health (allergies, vector-borne diseases from ticks, etc.) => social cost
- Risk of falling trees => social or economic cost, depending on the perspective
- Nuisances, such as falling leaves => social cost

¹ Ecosystem disservices (EDS) have been defined as “the ecosystem generated functions, processes and attributes that result in perceived or actual negative impacts on human wellbeing” (Shackleton et al., 2016)

2.2.4 Step 3: Advancing urban forests with a PESTEL analysis of actions that can be taken

A PESTEL analysis categorises participants' ideas for actions that can advance urban forests in their local area as Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental or Legal in nature? This exercise gives cities ideas from a perspective they might not have heard before.

The PESTEL analysis is a two-step approach:

1. Brainstorm on actions that can overcome the challenges related to urban forests and urban trees in your city, that increase the benefits provided while reducing the costs associated.
2. Categorise these actions along the PESTEL framework.

Figure 4: Advancing urban forests

Below are a few examples. Ideally, participants would be more specific about the specific benefits and challenges:

- Economic: developing a citizen-managed or non-profit budget for tree planting in parks and along streets
- Social: Hold community tree-planting events to boost the canopy cover in a city
- Technological: Inform citizens about geo-specific mobile apps that they can use to learn about and report certain risks (e.g., FleaTick Risk), so as to minimize this impact while still encouraging citizens to get outdoors

2.2.5 Step 4: Questions for research

The last template section (Questions for research) is a much shorter session, of about 15 minutes. This session is meant to develop research questions for CLEARING HOUSE, based on the discussions

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they had during the workshop (coffee breaks included). and can also add questions from their personal knowledge and experiences.

Facilitators may have to help participants get started and may need to probe for questions. Examples of leading questions to ask participants include:

- Reflecting on all workshop sessions, what questions would you like to be answered by the CLEARING HOUSE research team?
- What from the « Advancing Urban Forests » (PESTEL template) are you unsure of?
- What would be good to know about urban forests for your job?
- What are you curious to learn from other cities?

Figure 5: Questions for research

2.3 Sample agenda

Table 1 provides a sample agenda. The idea is for each case study to tailor the schedule to their individual circumstances, while keeping within the parameters of the workshop. For example, some cities may want to add a field trip on to the agenda, others may already have an existing workshop series running in which the co-design workshops are integrated. However, in order to allow for a more thorough comparison of results, the time allotted to each workshop session and the topics discussed during those sessions should not change.

Table 1: Sample agenda

Time	Session
8:30-9:00	Registration & Coffee
9:00-9:10	Welcome & Short ice-breaker
9:10-9:20	Setting the scene: Examples from other cities (e.g., short videos) OR introducing the local case
9:20-10:10	Major challenges to progress, implementation, governance & management
10:10-10:30	Coffee/Tea Break
10:30-11:20	Assessment of current tools & impacts of urban forests
11:20-11:40	Coffee/Tea Break
11:40-12:30	Advancing urban forests with a PESTEL analysis of actions that can be taken

12:30-12:45	Questions for research
12:45-13:30	Networking lunch

As many workshop participants will not know each other, it is useful for the facilitators to conduct a short ice-breaker right after the opening/welcome. This can be a quick game, a “Round Robin”² introduction of everyone, or even just asking people to say what they ate for breakfast. By putting people at ease, the conversations should flow more freely throughout the workshop.

Some case studies have expressed an interest to start the workshops with examples of what other cities are doing when it comes to urban forests. If a speaker is not available, facilitators could show a short online video of best practices. However, facilitators are reminded to keep this part short, as the focus of the workshops is collecting information from the case study, not the other way around.

Similarly, some city representatives may want to provide a short, 5-10 minute introduction about the state of urban forests in their area, including any relevant past or current information, such as key historical moments or the political environment surrounding urban forests. If this is the case, it is advised to do so either in place of examples from other cities, or to work this part into the first template session (Major challenges to progress, implementation, governance and management). Facilitators must ensure the cities do not go over a presentation time of 10 minutes, so as to keep the workshops on track. It is advised for city representatives to review the workshop templates before the workshops are held, so that they can focus the information they provide on the templates.

Lastly, facilitators have a fair amount of homework to do before the workshops. In addition to organising the workshops, they also need to complete “Part I - Before the workshop” of the workshop documentation. Furthermore, it would be useful if the facilitators could collect city/regional canopy cover and other maps related to the subject of urban forests. These can serve as visuals that can be referenced upon by the participants and city representatives during the workshop.

2.4 Target Stakeholders

A stakeholder is anyone who has a professional, public or private stake in the topic of the workshop. Stakeholders related to urban forest and urban trees range from individual citizens, over civil society organisations and businesses to civil servants, decision-makers and experts (including scientists).

2.4.1 Stakeholder mapping & identification

We consider four steps to select stakeholders for the workshops (CLEEN, 2016):

- 1) Identifying: listing relevant groups, organizations, and people;
- 2) Analysing: understanding stakeholder relationships, perspectives and interests;
- 3) Mapping: visualizing relationships to objectives and other stakeholders;
- 4) Prioritizing: ranking stakeholder relevance and identifying issues.

1. Identifying potential stakeholders

² Each person presents themselves by answering one or several creative questions, as a different way of presenting themselves (for example “If I were a dish, I would be a ... because ...”)

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The first step in the mapping process is to understand that there is no magic list of stakeholders. Most cities or urban forest managers have a list of organisations and agencies with a stake in urban forest and greenspace management. This list is a good start for identifying the potential invitees, but the final list will depend on the specific characteristic of the workshop (location, topic, ...). The list can also change during the course of the workshops and its preparation. Methods available for identifying stakeholders include use of local knowledge, document analysis, focus groups, snowball sampling, semi-structured interviews, self-selection or participant observation (De Vreese, 2018).

2. Analysing: understanding stakeholder relationships, perspectives and interests

A next step is to analyse the topical focus and the perspective stakeholders offer, their stake in the topic, and their relationship to the issue(s) and each other. The following criteria (CLEEN 2016) help to analyse each identified stakeholder and to prioritise them:

- Expertise: Does the stakeholder have information, counsel, or expertise on the issue that could be helpful to your undertaking?
- Willingness to engage: How willing is the stakeholder to engage?
- Influence: How much influence does the stakeholder have? (You will need to clarify “who” they influence, e.g., other NGOs, companies, the public, investors, etc.).
- Necessity of involvement: Is this someone who could derail or delegitimize the process if they were not included in the engagement? This is also related to aspects of power.
- Interest: is the issue of interest to the stakeholder and does it overlap with the focus of the stakeholder?

Based on the list resulting from step 1, a table can be developed in which the prospective stakeholders are categorised according to their compliance with the four criteria above. The results from this table gives an indication on which stakeholders should be involved.

An interesting method to complement the above, is the radical transactiveness method (Hart and Sharma 2004). This method aims at including stakeholders representing known but missing stances and opens a dialogue with stakeholders who can be considered peripheral but whose views may be disruptive.

3. Mapping stakeholders

- The information from the table in Step 2 can be used to produce stakeholder maps that help to visualize the roles, stake and relationships of the stakeholders to the issue, and the relationships between the stakeholders. Stakeholder maps are charts that depict one of the following interrelationships (CLEEN, 2016; De Vreese, 2018): Interest-influence chart: maps the influence of the stakeholders on the decision-making process or the management of (natural) resources, versus their stakes and interest;
- Power-interest chart: is similar, but focusses on the power of the stakeholder in decision-making versus the interest in the topic;
- importance-influence chart: classifies stakeholders according to the degree of importance in the decision-making process, and according to the degree they can influence ecosystems;
- expertise-willingness to participate chart: maps the expertise of the stakeholder versus the willingness to engage in the workshops.

The charts can be made three-dimensional by integrating a third criteria to give weight to the dot defining the stakeholder (small, medium or large circles denoting the interest for example).

Arrows between the dots (stakeholders) can depict influence, or the relationships between actors (conflictual, complementary or cooperative, Reed et al. 2009).

4. Prioritising stakeholders

Based on the information in the steps above, workshop organisers can select the most relevant stakeholders.

Below, we provide some examples of stakeholders that can be involved in the co-design workshops

1. Policymakers & civil servants

- City case study representatives
- Government employees (national, regional, local and district levels)
- Water, landscape and greenspace authorities
- Forest and nature managers
- Urban planners
- Road management agencies
- Leisure & recreation area managers
- Environment and/or Climate Departments

Due to historical and management reasons, the local department in charge of managing urban greenspace often varies from city to city. Regardless of the department, policymakers as a group often directly affect urban forest management or urban forest implementation. Policymakers can also be from international, national, or regional government agencies.

In China, workshop organizers will select policymakers from forestry or garden bureaus (national, provincial, municipal or district level), which carry the responsibility for urban trees, forests and the construction and management of urban greenspace.

The responsibility for urban trees and urban forests is also dispersed in European cities. Diverging city departments are involved (road agencies, park departments, leisure and recreation services, nature and forest agencies), but also diverging government levels can have a role (from district park departments to national forest agencies).

2. Businesses

- Landscaping companies
- Environmental design companies
- Landscape architects
- Consultants
- Real estate developers
- Retail
- Business councils

Businesses involved also include companies active in planning, designing, establishing and managing urban forests, as business actors who are interested in trading in an attractive environment.

In China, workshops organizers will focus on several famous companies that play important roles in urban forestry, such as the Urban Construction Group Co. Ltd., and Greentown Real Estate Group Co. Ltd. Landscaping companies in China are the main performers of urban green space improvement. In the process of urban afforestation, the businesses are more concerned about economic benefits,

management and maintenance costs. Obtaining opinions from relevant companies is also constructive for urban green space construction.

European business partners are more related to business councils and the retail sector, as beneficiaries of a green environment. The level of involvement and responsibility of business partners in greenspace management diverges from country to country, and from city to city: some cities have outsourced the whole planning and management cycle of urban greenspace provision and management, other cities are still doing all planning and management tasks inhouse with own staff.

3. Citizens & Civil Society Groups

- Forest & nature conservancy groups
- Less-privileged societal groups (elderly, women, ethnic minorities, people with disabilities, immigrant groups ...)
- Health care
- Social care
- Neighbourhood committees
- Schools, pre-schools, day care
- Youth organisations
- Sports organisations

This group includes direct stakeholders and also vulnerable populations (for example poor, old or disabled people as well as new immigrants or marginalised genders), whose opinion is often ignored in policy formulation and implementation. Participants can be selected from local institutions and community groups. Workshop organizers will also collaborate with several local volunteer groups (e.g. Nature School in Shenzhen) to select representative citizens. The way to involve the vulnerable groups will depend on a case-to-case basis, and more specific guidelines will be shared once this has been tested out with the city case studies.

4. Experts & Scientists

- Research institutes
- University professors
- Graduate students
- Health experts
- Professional networks (botanists, sector associations etc.)

Experts and scientists hold professional opinions toward urban forests. They can be selected from research institutes and universities, or from professional organisations.

3 Co-design Workshop: Implementation

3.1 Tips for a successful event

- 5) Send a **save-the-date** at least **3 months** before the workshop. People have busy calendars! During those few months, employ multiple tactics to advertise the workshop (face-to-face, social media, flyers, local media outlets, etc.)
- 6) Invite participants from across the spectrum. The more **diversity**, the greater the potential of varied responses. Think of diversity not just in terms of job roles, but also cultural upbringing, gender, social class, etc.
- 7) **Location!** Hold the workshops in a space easily accessible to all (people with disabilities, accessibility by public transport), equipped with a screen projector and several tables for small-group collaboration. Flip-charts are also nice to have, as it gives groups the flexibility to stand up

and discuss in less-traditional ways.

- 8) Have **communication material** about the project visible at the event (project logo, flyers, rollup, etc.)
- 9) Prepare to have at least **one facilitator for every 8-10 participants (max)**. The facilitators will lead the workshop sessions and answer participants' questions. Facilitators will need to be very familiar with the session templates before the workshops begin.

3.2 Preparation phase

3.2.1 *To do's*

Three months before the event:

- Build the organization team (coordination, logistics, communication, facilitators)
- Detail aims of the local workshops (tailor the general aims as set in chapter 2 to the local situation, tying in with local processes)
- Decide timing and location, define agenda
- Define target groups, identify potential stakeholders select stakeholders to be invited and send out invitations;
- Define local dissemination strategy
- Post on social media and communicate on the event regularly (every 1 or 2 weeks)
- Collect and prepare communication material (logo, workshops slogan, local flyers...)
- Translate documents (workshop slides, A3 templates, attendance sheet, consent form...)

At least three weeks before the event:

- Post on social media and communicate more regularly on the event (weekly and then 1 week before, 3 days before and 1 day before)
- Send participants the information sheet and the informed consent form
- Refine/ Finalize agenda based on speakers available
- Prepare logistics and brief logistics team
- Prepare participant name tags
- Optional: plan a visual facilitator

Facilitators:

- Get familiar with the workshop methodology;
- Prepare information in advance (existing tools & policies, find canopy cover & other maps...);
- Fill out and send the workshop documentation form "Part I - Before the workshop" (pre-workshops part), prepare definition of UF-NBS for the intro

3.2.2 *Inputs for the workshop*

All documents are available at the [CLEARING HOUSE co-design page](#) at Zenodo.org.

- Workshop guidelines (this file)
- 1. Workshop documentation sheet (<https://zenodo.org/record/3886682>)
- 2. Attendance sheet (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886773>)

D3.1_ Guidance document for the local co-design and co-learning workshops

- 3. Support slides (intro to CH project and UF-NBS definition) + A3 templates of the methodology graphic support (see Figure 2 to 5) (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886897>)
- Communication material
 - 4. Official project poster (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/3886806>)
 - 5. Workshop flyer templates (to be adapted by each city/ region) (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886824>)
 - 6. Existing videos online for the intro (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886878>)
 - 7. Project logo and project ppt (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886917>)
- 8. Consent form related to ethics (<https://www.zenodo.org/deposit/3886921>)

3.3 Workshop day

3.3.1 Guidelines for workshop facilitation (Five P's)

Participation

Participants should be encouraged to speak up and engage with one another. The goal is to have their feedback, not teach them something.

Pauses

The workshops will last three hours. Facilitators should ensure the discussions stay on-track. However, coffee/tea breaks are important to give participants a chance to network and refresh their minds. Individuals should feel free to take breaks during the workshops.

Positivity

There are no bad ideas. Workshops are a time to think creatively, not negatively. Criticising or discounting others' ideas will not be accepted.

Punctuality

It is imperative that the workshop run on-time. For this, it is good to have a designated time keeper. Print time cards for « 5 minutes » and « 1 minute », as they can help visually.

Power

Facilitators should ensure that everyone get the word and get heard. Facilitators have an important role to avoid that powerful voices take over the debate.

3.3.2 To do's

- Equipment: post its, pens, flipchart, beamer and clicker, extra paper
- Participant name tags
- Print the following documents which are available on [CLEARING HOUSE co-design page](#) at Zenodo.org:
 - A3 templates of the methodology graphic support (see Figure 2 to 5), to be printed as workshop support documents and filled-out with post-its by the participants during the workshop
 - 5min and 1min A4 pages for speakers to signal time during presentations
 - Attendance sheet
 - Communication material (project logo, flyers, rollup, etc.)

- Canopy cover & other area maps that you may have and which could be handy in support of the discussion
- Take photos and videos (define who will be in charge)
- Post on social media (define who will be in charge)

3.3.3 Communication tips

In order to communicate on the event and ensure that workshop participants also communicate within the same framework, it is important to follow the following steps:

- Establish the workshop official hashtags and display them on a sheet of paper in the event room in order for the participants to have easy access to it (for example #UF-NBS #UF-NBScodesign and possibly an equivalent hashtag in the local language);
- Display WIFI credentials for participants to access the internet;
- Display the main social media accounts names of the organizers in order to facilitate tagging (for example: Twitter handles and Instagram accounts);
- Encourage people to share pictures and insights on social media;
- Take pictures of workshop activities (verify people's consent and privacy rules) and post them on social media;
- With the local organizers team, communicate on the highlights and main learnings of the workshop;
- End with a group picture!

3.4 Follow-up phase

3.4.1 To do's

- Communicate on social media and to the participants the results of the workshops, photos and highlights, and mention the next steps;
- Plan a post-workshop communication plan to keep regular communication (monthly) until the next workshop (for example a monthly e-newsletter);
- Facilitators complete "Part II – Workshop summary" of the workshop documentation.

Once the workshops are over, facilitators have one more task: complete "Part II – Workshop summary" of the workshop documentation. This includes a summary of the discussions and template findings and should be complemented with any notes that the facilitators took during the workshops. It is advised that facilitators complete and submit this form along with Part I shortly after the workshops, so that the information is still fresh in their minds. This part is crucial to the project's analysis, as the workshops will be conducted in the local language and the results need to be compared. Facilitators may feel free to contribute any questions they have to the knowledge gaps and research questions.

4 Co-learning Workshops: Methodology

Deepening the work of the co-design phase, two series of co-learning workshops will be organized: the first series to introduce the research work on UF-NBS and fit it to the specific context of the local case studies; and the second one to report and discuss findings from the analysis of UF-NBS with local stakeholders and citizens.

1. Methodology for the first series of co-learning workshops

The first series of workshops will be organized around a first introductory session that will present the main topics of research on UF-NBS in the project, followed by an exchange between participants and local cases study coordinators to detail the local research approach (with particular attention towards the involvement of citizens, civil society organisations and less-privileged groups in the research work). These workshops will last half a day.

Below is a tentative outline for the workshop:

- Introduction of research work: challenges and proposition of tools & actions (30min)
- Collaborative group sessions to adapt the research work to the local context, involve citizens in the research work (30 minutes), and reflect on possible tools and actions (30 min adapt & involve + 30 min tools & actions)
- Presentation by every group representative and general assessment of group work (30min)

2. Methodology for the second series of co-learning workshops

The second series of co-learning workshops aims at reporting and discussing the findings from the analysis of UF-NBS, particularly at the local level in the case study. To this end, these workshops will start with a presentation of a case study analysis as well as a presentation of the pilot tools tested locally.

Below is a tentative outline for the workshop:

- Presentation of UF-NBS case studies analysis (30 min)
- Presentation of pilot tools for UF-NBS (30 min)
- Divided in groups, the participants and the local case study coordinators discuss the findings presented, analysing what are the impacts of these findings and how they apply to the local context. Participants list their ideas, propositions, and questions under several categories (1h with a rotation of groups after 30min):
 - enhancement of the resilience of the urban socio-ecological system
 - cost effectiveness,
 - governance, settings
 - involvement of different societal groups (government, businesses, gender and culturally defined citizens, civic associations, and other intermediaries)
 - impact of diverging planning traditions, practices and discourses on UF-NBS delivery
- Presentation of the work of the different groups (30min).

5 Contact

If you wish to know more and implement this approach in your local city/ region, please get in touch with our project contact points in Europe and China:

- EU: Dr Rik De Vreese, European Forest Institute (EFI), rik.devreese@efi.int
- China: Dr Jiali Jin, Chinese Academy of Forestry (CAF), jinjiali@caf.ac.cn

6 CONCLUSION

This document aims to share the developed methodology, so that the case cities can organize the co-design and co-learning workshops successfully and develop a society-wide perspective on urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS). It can help the local co-design workshops explore the states of the respective UF-NBS in specific cases, major challenges relating to the further progress and implementation of the UF-NBS, and challenges relating to UF-NBS governance, UF-NBS management, as well as wider ecological and societal impacts provided by UF-NBS. This document also gives practical guidelines for co-learning workshops to help local case study coordinators enhance the communications with stakeholders and citizens, which can help them to understand the needs and opinions of the people who are affected by the UF-NBS.

We hope this approach and methodology will have inspired you and we look forward to hearing about you if you plan to implement it.

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